

THE WAY OF TEACHING ENGLISH USING INTERESTING ACTIVITIES, ROLE PLAYS AND LANGUAGE SKILLS DURING ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract. *The right position and the way of using interactive methods during English lessons for none specialized students are discussed in this article.*

Key words: *language skills, role plays, complex cognitive, physical and social interaction, activities.*

Today students' interests in foreign languages are improving day by day. During the past two decades, the exercise of spoken language skills has received increasing attention among educators.

Foreign language curricula focus on productive skills with special emphasis on communicative competence. Students' ability to engage in meaningful conversational interaction in the target language is considered an important, if not the most important, goal of language education. This shift of emphasis has generated a growing need for instructional materials that provide an opportunity for controlled interactive speaking practice outside the classroom.

We see almost daily in our classroom a learner with high quantitative and analytical intelligence that is not guaranteed success in language learning. Further, many of our brightest and fastest language learners may even show relatively low levels of ability in quantitative and analytical types of reasoning.

The scientists propose some types of personal capability that, in his view, better define that complex cognitive, physical, and social interactions which determine the intelligence and abilities of a human being. These categories are: verb linguistic intelligence, professional intelligence, musical intelligence, logical intelligence, interpersonal self-knowledge intelligence.

The work is designed to help foreign language teaching professionals to see the concept of intelligence in a new light in order to broaden its traditionally narrow definition and develop awareness of learner differences, with the goal of introducing classroom approaches and techniques that will better meet the needs of individuals within the learning collective.

Games and fun activities play important role during the lessons of English language. It doesn't matter if we're teaching adults or children, games will liven up your lesson and ensure that your students will leave the classroom wanting more.

Games can be used to warm up the class before your lesson begins, during the lesson to give students a break when you're tackling a tough subject, or at the end of class when you have a few minutes left to kill. There are many games that we can play with students.

Guess the word

- Split the class into 2 teams, or more if you have a large class.
- Elect one person from each team to sit in the Hot Seat, facing the classroom with the board behind them.

- Write a word on the board. One of the team members of the student in the hot seat must help the student guess the word by describing it. They have a limited amount of time and cannot say, spell or draw the word.

- Continue until each team member has described a word to the student in the Hot Seat.

Health and illness

- Write ailments or problems related to your most recent lesson on post-it notes and stick one post-it note on each student's back.

- The students must mingle and ask for advice from other students to solve their problem.
- Students should be able to guess their problem based on the advice they get from their peers.

- Use more complicated or obscure problems to make the game more interesting for older students. For lower levels and younger students, announce a category or reference a recent lesson, like "Health", to help them along.

Make up sentences

This game requires some planning before the lesson.

- Write out a number of sentences, using different colors for each sentence. I suggest having 3-5 sentences for each team.

- Cut up the sentences so you have a handful of words.
- Put each sentence into hats, cups or any objects you can find, keeping each separate.
- Split your class into teams of 2, 3, or 4. You can have as many teams as you want but remember to have enough sentences to go around.
- Teams must now put their sentences in the correct order.
- The winning team is the first team to have all sentences correctly ordered.

There is also several kind of way of learning English language. But it will be more effective when you use all language skills: reading, writing, listening and speaking.

1. Listening

Listening is not only hearing but also understanding what is being said. In general there are two kinds of listening: active where we are in a face to face conversation or on the phone, etc; and passive when we watch television or listen to the radio.

Within this skill area there are also sub-skills which need to be learned. These include learning to "hear" the boundaries between words; learning to understand what a change in intonation or stress means and so on.

2. Speaking

As with listening, speaking can be active or passive. Active speaking is when we speak on the phone or face to face and there is interaction between the speaker and listener. Passive speaking is when we speak with no interruptions or feedback from others e.g. giving a speech or a teacher droning on and on and on!

Sub-skills here include pronunciation as well as using stress and intonation in the correct way. There are also more semantic skills such as how to choose the correct word and building an argument, etc.

3. Reading

Reading is well developed in most societies. Sub-skills here include deciphering the script (e.g. the Roman alphabet or Cyrillic or Chinese characters), recognizing vocabulary and picking out key words in the text. Here a knowledge of syntax comes into play and also the ability to transfer what is written into real-life knowledge.

There are also important reading sub-skills such as skimming, reading for gist, reading for detail and so on. These all have to be taught to students.

4. Writing

Sub-skills here include spelling and punctuation, using the correct vocabulary and of course using the correct style whether that be formal, poetic or whatever the occasion demands, from a shopping list to wedding vows.

These days as well there is not only the physical ability to use a pen and write but also the use of a keyboard or keypad.

So you were given the explanation of the language skills. The following advices are how to improve your language skills:

Reading is very important to all of us. It builds our knowledge, it gives us an escape, and it exercises our brains. The more you read, the better your reading skills and pronunciation will improve. Read on topics you're interested in, be it a romance novel, a sports magazine, newspaper or a car engine manual.

Try your hand at writing a novel, a short story, a poem, a play, or any other kind of creative writing. If you work at it bit by bit each day, it will hone your writing skills as well as exercise your creativity.

While you're listening, write down good notes and important details he/she says. Block distracting things from your mind. Listen to other people speaking the same language to improve your speaking and writing and pronunciation.

Take a topic and explain it. And a be sure to talk loud enough so people can hear and speak with little words and big words mixed together. Discuss the topic of your speech with others. Communicate a lot.

Select the details from the text read in Part 1 and have written down in Part 2. Explain the details out loud. Make reference to the text to support your inferences, points of view and opinions.

Explore the language features and their effects. When speaking, use figurative language to clarify your points, for example: similes, personification, metaphor, etc. Use short sentences to make the points clearer. **Identify and explain the author's purpose.** Discuss this with others if possible.

- Analyze the author's range of vocabulary. How does the author convey messages, moods, attitudes and feelings?¹

Experienced language teachers know that individual learners have distinct sets of personality characteristics which determine their talents, abilities, and preferences in language learning: some learners are «quick», some are thoughtful, some love to work independently, others requires explanations, guidance, and constant attention from the teacher.

That's why we must use the most effective teaching methods and aids at our disposal.

Role-plays, language skills, projects, video situations, games, activities can greatly widen our horizons of creativity within the suggested methods.

Nowadays the whole English Language Teaching community is entering a new stage of interactive learning by means of new technologies.

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